

(RESEARCH ARTICLE)

Survey and revision of storage insects from several localities of Iraq

Hanaa H. Al-Saffar and Razzaq Shalan Augul *

Iraq Natural history Research Center and Museum, University of Baghdad, Baghdad, Iraq.

GSC Biological and Pharmaceutical Sciences, 2022, 20(03), 175–186

Publication history: Received on 04 August 2022; revised on 13 September 2022; accepted on 15 September 2022

Article DOI: <https://doi.org/10.30574/gscbps.2022.20.3.0351>

Abstract

Due to the importance of insects present in storages, which cause a lot of damage to stored materials (cereals, seeds, dates and other materials), the current study was proposed to determine the species spread in Iraq. It showed 31 species belonging to 16 genera under eight families and two orders. The specimens were collected from several storage spaces at several regions of Iraq. The species of *Tribolium castaneum* (Herbst, 1797) was most abundant population compared with other insects.

The study also included a revision of the species that recorded previously in Iraq.

Keywords: Cereals; Iraq; Revision; Storage insects; Survey

1. Introduction

The different products (cereals and foods) are stored in many places, like the kitchen or other storage places may become infested with various species of insects which belong to diverse orders that referred to as "pantry pests." These insects eat or contaminate the materials stored, thus making it inadequate for human consumption; also may be uncomfortable, because of they often leave the infested products and walking or fly inside the house [1].

Many insects may infest the grain in storage; the main pests that cause harm are: the adult and larval stages of coleopteran species and the larval stage of moths. All are most likely a causing trouble with their presence, whether live or dead, in grains that are to be processed for eating [2]. The major insect species in the distribution warehouses and stores are *Plodia interpunctella* (Hübner, 1813) (Lepidoptera, Pyralidae) and *Tribolium castaneum* (Herbst, 1797) (Coleoptera, Tenebrionidae); for domestic animal food at retail stores, the species of *Sitophilus* C. J. Schoenherr, 1838 (Coleoptera, Curculionidae) have been shown to be a damaging [3]. To addition, the main pest species at mills are *T. castaneum* and *P. interpunctella*; on the other hand, it has been found that the members of the genus *Sitophilus* are a problem for pasta at food processors [4, 5].

The aim of this study is to survey and revised checklist the store insect species in Iraq.

2. Material and methods

The adults and larvae specimens were collected from different localities of Iraq during the year 2021; they collected by hands and others by the aid of sieves specially the red flour beetles, and then killed by freezing for 24 hours.

* Corresponding author: Razzaq Shalan Augul

Iraq Natural history Research Center and Museum, University of Baghdad, Baghdad, Iraq.

Some specimens were mounted by insect pins and other small by triangular labels and put in collecting boxes. The specimens were stored at the department of Entomology and Invertebrates, Iraq Natural history Research Center and Museum.

The specimens were identified by authors at level families, genera and species when possible in this survey and used different taxonomical keys such as: [6, 7, 8, 9, 10, 11, 12, 13, 14, 15]. The synonyms of the species are given according to [16].

3. Results and discussion

The investigation showed 31 species belonging to 16 genera under 8 families and 2 orders as below:

3.1. Order: Coleoptera

3.1.1. Family: Anobiidae

Genus *Lasioderma* Stephens, 1835

Synonyms:

Hypora Mulsant & Rey, 1864

Ladioderma Loeding, 1945

Lasiderma Schilsky, 1899-01

Lasioderma Dejean, 1833

Lassioderna Mukerji, 1955-01

Losioderma Borror & DeLong, 1954

Pseudochina Jacquelin du Val, 1860

Pseudochinus Zoological Record, 1865

Tasioderma Chenu, 1884

Lasioderma serricorne Fabricius, 1792

Common name: Cigarette beetle.

Synonyms:

Lasioderma brevis (Wollaston, 1861)

Lasioderma castaneum Melsheimer, 1846

Lasioderma fuscum (Rey, 1892)

Lasioderma testaceum (Duftschmid, 1825)

Lasioderma testaceum Stephens, 1835

Lasioderma torquatum (Thomson, 1859)

Pseudochina fuscum Rey, 1892

Ptilinus serricorne Fabricius, 1792

Ptilinus testaceus Duftschmid, 1825

Ptinus serricorne Fabricius, 1792

Ptinus serricornis Fabricius, 1792

Xyletinus brevis Wollaston, 1861

Xyletinus torquatum Chevrolat, 1859

Material examined: 30 specimens from storage spices during 22-31.iii.2021, Al-Kadhomyia district, Baghdad.

Distribution: Iraq [17]; Syria [18]; widely distributed in Africa, Asia, Europe, North and South America and Oceania [19].

3.1.2. Family: Bostrichidae

Genus *Rhyzopertha* Stephens, 1830

Rhyzopertha dominica (Fabricius, 1792)

Common name: Lesser grain borer.

Synonyms:

Synodendron dominicum Lesne, 1898

Material examined (9 specimens): This species collected from stored grains; 3♂♂, 4♀♀, 7.vii.2018, Wasit Province, Az Zubaydiyah District . 2 ♂♂, 3.viii.2021, Diyala Province, Al Khalis District.

Distribution: Iraq [17]; Cosmopolitan species [20].

Genus *Lyctus* Fabricius, 1792

Synonyms:

Eulyctus Jacobson, 1916

Lictus Melsheimer, 1806

Lygdus Fabricius, 1792

Xylotrogus Stephens, 1830

Lyctus brunneus (Stephens, 1830)

Common name: Powderpost beetles.

Synonyms:

Lyctus carolina Casey, 1891=

Lyctus costatus Blackburn, 1888

Lyctus disputans Walker, 1858

Lyctus jatrophae Wollaston, 1867

Lyctus withdrawn Walker, 1858

Lyctus rugulosus Montrouzier, 1861

Xylotrogus brunneus Stephens, 1830

Material examined: (30 specimens): 20 specimens, 21.iii.2021, Baghdad Province, Al-Kadhimiya District; 6 specimens, 10.iv.2021, Karbala Province, Karbala City; 4 specimens, 8.v.2018 from old furniture, Najaf, City center.

Distribution: Iraq [21]. This species is widely distribution in Palaearctic Region [22], such as: Algeria [23], Egypt [24], Taiwan [25], Austria [26]; Korea [27], Iran [28] and Himalayas [15].

3.1.3. Family: Chrysomelidae

Genus *Callosobruchus* Pic, 1902

Callosobruchus maculatus Fabricius, 1775

Common name: Cowpea seed beetle.

Material examined (71 specimens): The specimens were collected from stored cowpea grains; 33 specimens, 9.v.2021, 16 specimens, 1.vi.2021, Baghdad City, Jisr Diyala District. 26 specimens, 22.vi.2021, Maysan Province, Amara City. 7 specimens, 11.vii.2021, Karbala Province, Karbala City. Distribution: Africa, tropical and sub-tropical parts of the world [29].

3.1.4. Family: Curculionidae

Genus *Sitophilus* Schoenherr, 1838

Sitophilus granarius (Linnaeus, 1758)

Common name: Granary weevil, grain weevil.

Synonyms:

Calandra granaria (Linnaeus, 1758)

Calandra granarius G. J. Billberg, 1820

Calandra laevicosta Philippi & Philippi, 1864

Cordyle granaria (Linnaeus, 1758)

Cordyle granarius (Linnaeus, 1758)

Curculio contractus E. L. Geoffroy, 1785

Curculio granarius Linnaeus, 1758

Curculio pulicarius G. W. F. Panzer, 1798

Curculio unicolor T. Marsham, 1802

Rhynchophorus granarius (Linnaeus, 1758)

Rhynchophorus ruber F. P. Schrank, 1798

Material examined (114 specimens): 30♂♂, 20 ♀♀, 13.x.2021, 20.x.2021, Baghdad Province, Baghdad, Shorja Marketplace, collected from oat. 12♂♂, 25 ♀♀, 20.x.2021, 30.xi.2021, Wasit Province, An-Nu'maniyah District, collected from wheat. 17♂♂, 10 ♀♀, 10.xii.2021, Diyala Province, Al Khalis District, collected from *Cicer* sp.

Distribution: Iraq [30]; Algeria, Argentina, Australia, Canada, Chile, Denmark, France, Italy, Poland, Russia, Spain, South Africa, Sweden, Thailand, UK and USA [31]; Japan [32]; Yemen [33].

Sitophilus linearis A. Hustache, 1930

Common name: Tamarind weevil.

Synonyms:

Calandra linearis Herbst, 1797

Cordyle striatus Thunberg, 1815

Rhynchophorus linearis Herbst, 1795

Distribution: Iraq [17]; Australia, Brazil, Costa Rica, Cuba, Kenya, Mexico, Spain, Ukraine and USA [16].

Sitophilus oryzae (Linnaeus, 1763)

Common names: Rice weevil, lesser grain weevil.

Synonyms:

Calandra funebris Rey, 1895

Calandra minor Sasaki, 1910

Calandra sasakii Takahashi, 1928

Curculio bituberculatus Fabricius, 1781

Curculio frugilegus De Geer, 1775

Curculio oryza Linnaeus, 1763

Material examined (50 specimens): The specimens collected from rice; 10 ♂♂, 9 ♀♀, 20.x.2021, Baghdad Province, Shorta Al Khamsa. 15♂♂, 11 ♀♀ at 5.x.2021; Wasit Province, Az Zubaydiyah District. 2♂♂, 3 ♀♀, 5.xi.2021, Saladin Province, Tikrit City.

Distribution: Widely distributed in Africa, Asia, Europe, North and South America and Oceania (34).

Sitophilus zeamais Motschulsky, 1855

Common names: Greater grain weevil, maize weevil.

Synonyms:

Calandra chilensis Philippi & Philippi, 1864

Calandra platensis Zacher, 1922

Sitophilus oryzae subsp. *zeamais* (Motschulsky, 1855)

Sitophilus zea-mais Motschulsky & V.de, 1855

Material examined (41 specimens): 7 ♂♂, 2 ♀♀, 22.xi.2021, Baghdad Province, Al-Mada'in District, the specimens were collected from private maize store. 2♂♂, 10 ♀♀, 5.x.2021, Wasit Province, Al-Aziziyah District, specimens were collected from a rice store; 11♂♂, 9 ♀♀, 10.x.2021, Diyala Province, Al-Muqdadia District, specimens were collected from private maize store.

Distribution: Widely distributed in Africa, Asia, Europe, North and South America and Oceania [35].

3.1.5. Family: Tenebrionidae

Genus *Alphitobius* Stephens, 1829

Synonyms:

Cryptops Solier, 1851

Heterophaga Dejean, 1834

Heterophaga Ludwig Redtenbacher, 1845

Latetribolium Lepesme, 1943

Microphyes MacLeay, 1873

Alphitobius diaperinus (Panzer, 1797)

Common name: Lesser mealworm.

Synonyms:

Alphitobius piceus (Olivier, 1792)

Tenebrio diaperinus Panzer, 1797

Material examined (10 specimens): 4♂♂, 6♀♀, 4.xi.2021, Baghdad Province, Al-Kadhimiya District, Aden Square; the specimens were collected from poultry food in a private store.

Distribution: Iraq [30]; Algeria, Austria, Australia, Belgium, Brazil, Canada, France, Greece, Germany, India, Norway, Korea, Lithuania, Mexico, Netherland, Poland, Poland, Spain, Sweden, Switzerland, Finland, USA, UK [16].

Genus *Latheticus* Waterhouse, 1880

Latheticus oryzae Waterhouse, 1880

Common name: Long headed flour beetle.

Material examined (22 specimens): The specimens collected from private store on rice, 3.vi.2021, Saladin Province, Samarra District.

Distribution: Iraq [36]; Australia, Egypt, France, Germany, Japan, KSA, Mexico, Mozambique, Netherlands, Poland, South Africa, Spain, Sweden, UK, USA and Yemen [16].

Genus *Tribolium* Macley, 1825

Synonyms:

Aphanotus Leconte, 1862

Eusemostene Gebien, 1940

Leanium Uyttenboogaart, 1934

Margus Dejean, 1834

Margus Redtenbacher, 1842

Stene Stephens, 1829

Tribolium Mulsant, 1854

Tribolium castaneum (Herbst, 1797)

Common name: Red flour beetle.

Synonyms:

Colydium castaneum Herbst, 1787

Tribolium navale (Fabricius, 1775)

Material examined (260 specimens): the specimens were collected from private stores on flour; 60 ♂♂, 60 ♀♀, 22.v.2021, Baghdad Province, Jaddria District. 27♂♂, 33 ♀♀, 5.vi.2021, Babylon Province, Al-Musayyib District. 30♂♂, 50 ♀♀, 10.vii.2021, Diyala Province, Baquba City.

Distribution: Worldwide distribution [37].

Tribolium confusum Jaquelin, 188

Common name: Confused flour beetles

Material examined: It was not recorded during our investigation throughout 2021.

Distribution: Iraq [38]; worldwide distributed [39].

3.1.6. Family: Dermestidae

Genus *Anthrenus* Geoffroy, 1762

Synonyms:

Anthremis Hope, 1845

Anthrenoides Beal, 2003

Anthrenops Reitter, 1880

Anthrenus Pic, 1937

Byrrhus Sulzer, 1776

Helcoernus Wu, 1937

Helocerus Mulsant & Rey, 1867

Hypoceuthes Gerstaecker, 1871

Peacockia Menier & Villemant, 1993

Ranthenus Mroczkowski, 1962

Setapeacockia Háva, 2008

Solskinus Mroczkowski, 1951

Anthrenus coloratus Reitter, 1881

Common name: Asian carpet beetle, carpet beetles.

Material examined (5 specimens): the specimens were collected from animal materials that stored in Iraq Natural History Research center and Museum, 1 ♂, 4 ♀♀, 30.vii.2021, Baghdad Province, Bab Al Muadham.

Distribution: Iraq [40]; Afghanistan, Algeria, Egypt, Eritrea, Guinea, India, Israel, Iraq, Japan, Kazakhstan, Kyrgyzstan, Morocco, Namibia, Oman, Qatar, Saudi Arabia, Sudan, Syria, Tadzhikistan, Tunisia, Turkey, Turkmenistan, United Arab Emirates, USA and Yemen [41, 42, 43]; Russia [44].

Anthrenus flavipes Le Conte, 1856

Common name: Furniture carpet beetle.

Synonyms:

Anthrenus fasciatus Reitter, 1881

Anthrenus vorax Waterhouse, 1883

Distribution: Iraq [40]; Cosmopolitan species [45].

Anthrenus pimpinellae Fabricius, 1775

Synonym:

Byrrhus pimpinellae Fabricius, 1775

Distribution: Iraq [46]; Asia and portions of the Oriental region; Europe, Northern Africa, introduced to parts of North America [47].

Anthrenus scrophulariae (Linnaeus, 1758)

Common name: Common carpet beetle, buffalo carpet beetle.

Synonyms:

Anthrenus scropulariae (Linnaeus, 1758)

Dermestes scrophulariae Linnaeus, 1758

Distribution: Iraq [30]; Austria, Australia, Belarus, Bulgaria, Canada, Croatia, Estonia, Finland, France, Germany, Hungary, Italy, Lithuania, Norway, Poland, Romania, Russia, Serbia, Slovakia, Sweden, Switzerland, Turkey, Ukraine, USA [16].

Anthrenus verbasci (Linnaeus, 1767)

Common name: Varied carpet beetle.

Synonyms:

Anthrenus florilegus Geoffroy, 1785

Anthrenus varius (F., 1775)

Byrrhus verbasci Linnaeus, 1767

Material examined: (21 specimens), it was collected from insects that preserved in the Iraq Natural History Research Center and Museum; Baghdad Province; Bab Al Muadham, 7 specimens, 23.v.2021; 5 specimens, 11.vi.2021; 9 specimens, 1.vi.2021.

Distribution: Iraq [43]; also this species distribute in most of Europe, Eastern Palearctic and Nearctic realm, North Africa and Neotropical [48].

Genus *Attagenus* Latreille, 1802

Synonyms:

Attagenus Háva, 2007

Brachysphyrus Blackburn, 1903

Eunorops Gistel, 1856

Lanorus Mulsant & Rey, 1868

Megatoma Kugelann, 1792

Pseudotelopes Pic, 1916

Telopes Redtenbacher, 1843

Telopus Mulsant & Rey, 1868

Attagenus bifasciatus (Olivier, 1790)

Synonym:

Dermestes bifasciatus Olivier, 1790

Distribution: Afghanistan; Algeria; Caucasus, Egypt, India, Iran, Iraq, Israel, Lebanon, Libya, Morocco, Palestine, Russia, Syria, Turkmenistan, Tunisia and Turkey [49].

Attagenus lobatus Rosenhauer, 1856

Synonyms:

Attagenus byturoides Solskij, 1876

Attagenus sericeus Reitter, 1881

Distribution: Iraq [46]; Afghanistan, Egypt, France, Italy, Mongolia, Spain, Sudan and USA [16].

Attagenus pellio (Linnaeus, 1758)

Common name: Fur beetle.

Synonyms:

Dermestes bipunctatus De Geer, 1774

Dermestes pellio Linnaeus, 1758

Distribution: Iraq [43]; Austria, Australia, Belgium, Denmark, Estonia, Finland, France, Germany, Italy, Lithuania, Luxembourg, Netherlands, Norway, Poland, Slovakia, Sweden, Switzerland, UK [16].

Attagenus unicolor (Brahm, 1790)

Common name: Black carpet beetle.

Synonyms:

Attagenus megatoma (Fabricius, 1798)

Attagenus piceus (Olivier, 1790)

Dermestes megatoma Fabricius, 1798

Dermestes piceus Olivier, 1790

Dermestes unicolor Brahm, 1790

Distribution: In Iraq, this species registered by [50] under the synonym name *Attagenus piceus* Olivier, 1790). Austria, Australia, Canada, Estonia, Finland, France, Germany, Greece, Italy, Japan, Korea, Poland, Portugal, Russia, South Africa, Spain, Sweden, Switzerland, Turkey, Ukraine and USA [16].

Genus *Dermestes* Linnaeus, 1758

Synonyms:

Dermalius Háva, 2001

Dermestaes Latreille, 1802

Dermestida Leach, 1815

Dermestinus Zhantiev, 1967

Dermestites Laporte de Castelnau, 1840

Montandonia Jacquet, 1886

Dermestes ater DeGeer, 1774

Common name: Black larder beetle

Synonyms:

Dermestes cadaverinus Fabricius, 1775

Dermestes hispidulus Montrouzier, 1860

Distribution: Cosmopolitan [51].

Dermestes frischii Kugelann, 1792

Common name: Dermestid beetle

Distribution: Cosmopolitan [51].

Dermestes maculatus DeGeer, 1774

Common name: Hide beetle

Synonyms:

Dermestes truncatus Casey, 1916

Dermestes vulpinus Fabricius, 1781

Distribution: Iraq [46]; USA, Canada, Hawaii, Southeast Asia, and Italy [52].

Genus *Phradonoma* Jacquelin du Val, 1859

Synonyms:

Orbeola Mulsant & Rey, 1867

Phraeonoma Pic, 1933

Phradonoma nobile (Rietter, 1881)

Synonyms:

Trogoderma nobile Reitter, 1881

Distribution: Iraq [46]; Afghanistan, Algeria, Cyprus, Egypt, England, Eritrea, Greece, India, Iran, Iraq, Israel, Jordan, Libya, Morocco, Namibia, Nigeria, Pakistan, Portugal, Qatar, Spain, South Africa, Sudan, Tanzania, Tunisia, Saudi Arabia, Syria, Tadjikistan, Turkmenistan, United Arab Emirates, Uzbekistan and Zimbabwe [42, 53].

Genus *Trogoderma* Dejean, 1821

Synonyms:

Acolpus Jayne, 1882

Asidora Mulsant & Rey, 1867

Ditorines Normand, 1935

Entomotrogus Ganglbauer, 1904
Eucnocerus Sharp, 1902
Eurhopalus Solier, 1849
Globicornis Mulsant & Rey, 1868
Macropirion Hope, 1840
Ocelliger Philippi, 1864
Psacus Pascoe, 1866
Pseudomegatoma Pic, 1915
Tragoderma, Deville 1935
Trochoderma Dahl, 1823
Trododerma Pic, 1950
Trogoderma Háva, 2007
Trogoderma Gistel, 1856

Trogoderma granarium Everts, 1898

Common name: Khapra beetle, cabinet beetle

Synonyms:

Trogoderma afrum Priesner, 1951

Trogoderma khapra Arrow, 1917

Material examined (47 specimens): 10 specimens, Wasit Province, Al-Aziziyah District, 19.v.2021; 23 specimens, 13.VI.2021, Dibuni District. Baghdad Province, Al-Mada'in District, 14 specimens, 29.iv.2021.

Distribution: Iraq [17]; Australia, Belgium, Egypt, Germany, India, Israel, Kenya, Korea, Netherlands, Pakistan, Sri Lanka, South Africa, Sweden, Switzerland, Syria, UK and USA [16].

Trogoderma variabile Ballion, 1878

Common name: Warehouse beetle

Synonyms:

Trogoderma parabile Beal, 1954

Trogoderma persica Pic, 1914

Distribution: Iraq [54]; Australia, Canada, Germany, Iran, Mexico, Sweden, UK and USA [16].

Trogoderma versicolor (Creutzer, 1799)

Synonym:

Anthrenus versicolor Creutzer, 1799

Distribution: Iraq [17]; Austria, France, Germany, Italy, Montenegro, Netherlands, Nicaragua, Spain, Sweden, Switzerland and USA [16].

3.1.7. Family: Silvanidae

Genus *Oryzaephilus* Ganglbauer, 1899

Oryzaephilus surinamensis (Linnaeus, 1758)

Common name: Saw-toothed grain beetle.

Synonyms:

Anobium frumentarium Fabricius, 1775

Dermestes sexdentatus Fabricius, 1792

Dermestes surinamensis Linnaeus, 1758

Oryzaephilus bicornis (Erichson, 1846)

Oryzaephilus cursor (Fabricius, 1792)

Oryzaephilus frumentarius (Fabricius, 1775)

Oryzaephilus sexdentatus (Fabricius, 1792)

Oryzaephilus sexdentatus (Herbst, 1783)

Silvanus bicornis Erichson, 1846

Silvanus surinamensis (Linnaeus)

Tenebrio cursor Fabricius, 1792

Materials examined (28 specimens): This species collected from date store; 9 specimens, 1.v.2021, Baghdad Province, Adhamiya District. 11 specimens, 17.vi.2022, Wasit Province, Al-Sawaira District. 8 specimens, 30.vi.2022, Diyala Province, Nahrawan District.

Distribution: World-wide distributed [55].

3.2. Order: Lepidoptera

3.2.1. Family: Pyralidae

Genus *Cadra* Walker, 1864

Synonym:

Xenephestia Gozmány, 1958

Cadra cautella (Walker, 1863)

Common name: Almond moth, date moth, dried currant moth, fig moth

Synonyms:

Cadra defectella Walker, 1864

Cadra desuetella (Walker, 1866)

Cadra formosella (Wileman & South, 1918)

Cadra irakella (Amsel, 1959)

Cadra passulella (Barrett, 1875)

Cadra rotundatella (Turati, 1930)

Ephestia cautella (Walker, 1863)

Ephestia passulella Barrett, 1875

Pempelia cautella Walker, 1863

Phycita formosella (Wileman & South, 1918)

Material examined (44 specimens): the species were collected from dates stores; 5♂♂, 11♀♀, 14.iv.2021, Baghdad Province, Karrada District; 7♀♀, 31.iv.2021, Abu-Ghraib. 2♂♂, 11♀♀, 11.v.2021, Al Anbar Province, Al-Karmah District. 8♂♂, 22.v.2021, Babylon Province, Al Eskandariya District.

Distribution: Cosmopolitan [56].

Genus *Ephestia* Guenee, 1845

Synonym:

Hyphantidium Scott, 1859

Ephestia kuehniella (Zeller, 1879)

Common name: Mediterranean flour moth.

Synonym:

Anagasta kuehniella (Zeller, 1879).

Ephestia fuscofasciella (Ragonot, 1887)

Ephestia gitonella (Druce, 1896)

Ephestia ischnomorpha (Meyrick, 1931)

Material examined (26 specimens): 5♂♂, 9♀♀, 17.iv.2021, Diyala Province; Baquba City. 7♂♂, 2♀♀, 2.vi.2021, Wasit Province, Az Zubaidiyah District. 2♂♂, 1♀, 22.iv.2021, Babylon Province, Hillah City.

Distribution: Cosmopolitan [57].

4. Conclusion

The investigation showed the beetles of the most important that attacked store materials in Iraq and caused damages. The current study is reviewed and updating the scientific names according to recent catalogues and checklists.

In addition to providing a unified list of those interested in this field, because the available data are scattered and not up to date. Therefore, the current study provides a solution to most of the inquiries related to the Iraqi storage insects' database as much as possible.

Compliance with ethical standards

Acknowledgments

The authors are grateful to the owners of private granaries, who help us when collecting the insects in different localities in Iraq.

Disclosure of conflict of interest

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

Funding

This work received no external funding.

References

- [1] Mason L J, Gibb T J. Insect pests of home stored foods E-37. Stored Product Pests, Purdue Extension. 2010; 4pp. Available at: <http://extension.entm.purdue.edu/publications/E-37.pdf>
- [2] Mason L J, Obermeyer J. Stored Product Pests. Purdue Extension E-66-W. 2010; Available at: <https://extension.entm.purdue.edu/publications/E-66.pdf>
- [3] Toews M, Subramanyam Bh, Roesli R. Development and validation of sequential sampling plans for *Sitophilus* species associated with pet specialty stores. p. 115–120. In: “Advances in Stored Product Protection” (P F Credland, D M Armitage, C H Bell, P M Cogan, E Highley, eds.). Proc. 8th Int. Working Conference on Stored Product Protection, York, UK, 22–26 July 2002. CABI International, Wallingford, UK. 2003; 1071 pp.
- [4] Chapman R N. The possibility of transmitting a *Calendra* infestation from wheat to macaroni thru the processes of milling and manufacturing. *Journal of Economic Entomology*. 1923, 16 (4): 341-348.
- [5] Babarinde G O, Babarinde S A, Ogunsola S O. Effect of maize weevil (*Sitophilus zeamais* Motschulsky 1855) infestation on the quality of three commercial pastas. *Food Science and Quality Management*. 2013, 21 (1): 1-11.
- [6] Crowson R A. The natural classification of the families of Coleoptera. Nathaniel Lloyd & Co., Ltd., London; 1955. 187 pp.
- [7] Crowson R A. Coleoptera: introduction and key to families. Handbooks for the identification of British insects. Royal Entomological Society of London, London; 1957. 59 pp.
- [8] Crowson R A. The natural classification of the families of Coleoptera. EW. Classey Ltd., Middlesex; 1967. 214 pp.
- [9] White R E. Key to North American Genera of Anobiidae, with Phylogenetic and Synonymic Notes (Coleoptera). *Annals of the Entomological Society of America*, 1971, 64(1): 179-191.
- [10] Bousquet Y. Beetles associated with stored products in Canada. Agriculture and Agri-Food Canada, Research Branch Agriculture, Canada Publication, 1990; 1837: 214pp.
- [11] Watt J C. Tenebrionidae (Insecta: Coleoptera). Catalogue of types and keys to taxa. *Fauna of New Zealand*, 1992; 26:1-70.
- [12] Háva J. World keys to the genera and subgenera of Dermestidae (Coleoptera), with descriptions, nomenclature and distributional records. *Acta Musei Nationalis Pragae, Series B, Historia Naturalis*. 2004; 60 (3-4): 149-164.
- [13] Háva J, Herrmann A, Clark W H. *Phradonoma nobile* (Reitter, 1881) (Coleoptera: Dermestidae), first record of the genus *Phradonoma* Jacquelin Du Val, 1859 in the Nearctic Region. *The Coleopterists Bulletin*. 2011, 65(4):434-435.
- [14] Lilligi M, Barthelet H B, Mifsud D. An identification and informative guide to the Tenebrionidae of Malta (Coleoptera). *Bulletin of the entomological Society of Malta*, 2012; 5: 121-160.
- [15] Liu L Y, Beaver R A. A synopsis of the powder post beetles of the Himalayas with a key to the genera (Insecta: Coleoptera: Bostrichidae). *Biodiversitat und Naturschutz Himalaya*, 2018; 6: 407-422.
- [16] GBIF Secretariat. GBIF Backbone Taxonomy. Checklist dataset <https://doi.org/10.15468/39omei> 2021. (Accessed via GBIF.org on 2022-03-27).
- [17] Hussain A A. Provisional list of insects pests and bibliography of insect fauna of Iraq. *Bulletin of College Science, University of Baghdad*, 1963; 7: 43-83.
- [18] Bilal H, Basheer A M, Saleh A T. Survey and abundance of common parasitoid and predatory species of the cigarette beetle, *Lasioderma serricorne* (F.) (Coleoptera: Anobiidae) in tobacco storage warehouses in Syria. *Egyptian Journal of Pest Control*. 2012, 21(2): 151-155.

- [19] CABI. *Lasioderma serricorne* (cigarette beetle). 2022. Available at: <https://www.cabi.org/isc/datasheet/29882#todistributionDatabaseTable>
- [20] Denux O, Zagatti P. Coleoptera families other than Cerambycidae, Curculionidae sensu lato, Chrysomelidae sensu lato and Coccinellidae Chapter 8.5. In: Roques, A.; Kenis, M.; Lees, D.; Lopez-Vaamonde, C.; Rabitsch, W.; Rasplus, J.-Y.; Roy, D. (eds) Alien terrestrial arthropods of Europe. *BioRisk*. 2010, 4(1): 315–406. doi: <https://doi.org/10.3897/biorisk.4.61>
- [21] Al-Saffar H H, Augul R S. Survey of true powder post beetles (Coleoptera, Lyctidae) in Iraq. 2019; Available at: https://www.researchgate.net/publication/350682476_Survey_of_True_Powder_Post_Beetles_Coleoptera_Lyctidae_in_Iraq
- [22] Borowski J. Bostrichidae. In: Löbl I, Smetana A (eds.) Catalogue of Palaearctic Coleoptera. Volume 4. Elateroidea – Derodontoidea– Bostrichoidea – Lymexyloidea – Cleroidea – Cucujoidea. Apollo Books, Stenstrup. 2007; p320–328.
- [23] Peyerimhoff P. de. Notes sur la biologie de quelques Coléoptères phytophages du Nord-Africain (troisième série) avec les descriptions de cinq espèces nouvelles et de sept sous-espèces ou variétés. *Annales de la Société Entomologique de France*. 1919; 8: 169-258.
- [24] Alfieri A. The Coleoptera of Egypt. *Memoires de la Societe entomologique d’Egypt*, 1976; 5: I-XVI + 1-362.
- [25] Liu L Y, Beaver R A, Yang G T. The Bostrichidae (Cpoleoptera) of Taiwan: a key to the species, new records, and a lectotype designation for *Sinoxylon mangiferae* Chujo. *Zootaxa*, 2006; 1307: 1-33.
- [26] Querner P, Morelli M, Oberthaler E, Strolz M, Schmitz Von Ledebur K, Zatschek I, Femi-Mebarek, A, Diehl J, Hölzl R, Engelhardt I, Krammer H, Fürnkranz S. Ten years of Integrated Pest Management (IPM) at the Kunsthistorisches Museum in Wien. *Journal of Entomological and Acarological Research Ser. II*. 2011, 43(2): 185–190.
- [27] Park S, Lee S, Hong K J. Review of the family Bostrichidae (Coleoptera) of Korea. *Journal of Asia Pacific Biodiversity*. 2015, (8): 298-304.
- [28] Liu L Y, Ghahri H, Beaver R A. An annotated synopsis powder post beetles of Iran (Coleoptera: Bostrichoidea: Bostrichidae). *Journal of insect Biodiversity*. 2016, 4(14): 1-22.
- [29] Beck C W, Blumer L S. A Handbook on bean beetles, *Callosobruchus maculatus*. National Science Foundation. 2014; 17pp. Available at: https://www.beanbeetle.org/new_website/wp-content/images/handbook.pdf
- [30] Derwesh A I. A preliminary list of identified insects and some arachnids of Iraq. *Direct. Gen. Agr. Res. and Proj. Baghdad. (Iraq), Bulletin*. 1965; 112: 128pp.
- [31] Champ B R, Dyte C E. Report of the FAO global survey of pesticide susceptibility of stored grain pests. 1976; FAO Plant Production and Protection Series No. 5. Rome, Italy: Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations.
- [32] Morimoto K. Check-list of the family Rhynchophoridae (Coleoptera) of Japan, with descriptions of a new genus and five new species. *Esakia*, 1978; 12:103-108.
- [33] Haines C P. Insects and arachnids from stored products: a report on specimens received by the Tropical Stored Products Centre 1973-77. Report of the Tropical Products Institute. 1981; L 54 iv+73 pp.
- [34] CABI. *Sitophilus oryzae* (lesser grain weevil). 2022. Available at: <https://www.cabi.org/isc/datasheet/10887#REF-DDB-15145> (Accessed on 30.03.2022)
- [35] CABI. *Sitophilus zeamais* (greater grain weevil). 2022. Available at: <https://www.cabi.org/isc/datasheet/10926> (Accessed on 30.03.2022)
- [36] Löbl I, Merkl O, Ando K, Bouchard P, Lillig M, Masumoto K, Schawaller W. Tenebrionidae. In: Löbl, I. & Smetana, A. (Eds.), Catalogue of Palaearctic Coleoptera. Vol. 5. Tenebrionoidea. Apollo Books, Stenstrup. 2008; p. 105-352.
- [37] Hill D S. Agricultural insect pests of the tropics and their control. In: *Agricultural insect pests of the tropics and their control*. Cambridge, UK: Cambridge University Press. 1975; 516 pp.
- [38] Khalaf K T. A collection of insects from Iraq. Iraq Natural History Museum Publication. 1959; 17: 1-26.
- [39] Cotton R T, Good N E. Annotated list of the insects and mites associated with stored grain and cereal products, and of their arthropod parasites and predators. United State, Department of Agriculture, Miscellaneous Publications. 1937; 258: 81pp.

- [40] Abdul- Rassoul M S. Insect pests infesting animal museum collection in Iraq. *Bulletin of the Iraq Natural History Museum*. 1996, 8 (4):1-7.
- [41] Zhantiev R D. Zhuki kozheedy fauny SSSR. [The skin eaters family Dermestidae of fauna of the USSR.] Izdatelstvo Moskovskogo Universiteta, Moskva. 1976; 180pp. (in Russian).
- [42] Háva J. World catalogue of the Dermestidae (Coleoptera). *Studie a Zprávy Oblastního Muzea Praha-východ v Brandýse nad Labem a Staré Boleslavi, Supplementum*. 2003; 1: 1-196.
- [43] Háva J. Dermestidae, pp. 57, 299-320. *In: Löbl, I. and Smetana, A. (eds.). Catalogue of Palaearctic Coleoptera. Volume 4. Elateroidea, Derodontoidea, Bostrichoidea, Lymexyloidea, Cleroidea and Cucujoidea. Apollo Books. Stenstrup. 2007; 935 pp.*
- [44] Kovalenko Y N. The first record of the alien species Asian carpet beetle (*Anthrenus coloratus* Reitter, 1881) (Coleoptera: Dermestidae) from Russia- A serious pest of museum collections. *Russian Journal of Biological Invasions*. 2018, 9(4):352-354. <https://doi.org/10.1134/S2075111718040070>
- [45] Háva J, Herrmann A. Checklist of Dermestidae (Insecta: Coleoptera: Bostrichoidea) of the United States. *Insecta Mundi*. 2021, 0871: 1–16. <https://digitalcommons.unl.edu/cgi/viewcontent.cgi?article=2367&context=insectamundi>
- [46] El-Haidari H, Fattah Y M, Sultan J A. Contribution to the insect fauna of Iraq (Part 4). *Dir. Gen. Plant Prot., (Iraq), Bulletin*. 1972, 18: 1-17.
- [47] Hoebeke E R, Wheeler A G Jr, Beal R S Jr. *Anthrenus pimpinellae* F., a Palearctic dermestid established in eastern North America (Coleoptera: Dermestidae). *Journal of the New York Entomological Society*. 1985, 93 (4): 1216–1222.
- [48] Robinson W H. *Handbook of urban insects and arachnids: A handbook of urban entomology*. Cambridge, Cambridge University Press. 2005; 472 pp. Available at: <http://www.bio-nica.info/biblioteca/Robinson2005UrbanInsects.pdf>
- [49] Háva J. *World Catalogue of insects. Vol. 13 Dermestidae (Coleoptera)*, Leiden, Netherlands, Brill. 2015; 419 pp.
- [50] Al-Ali A. *Phytophagous and entomophagous insects and mites of Iraq*. Iraq Natural History Museum Publication. 1977; 33: 1-142.
- [51] Mroczkowski M. New distributional data on Dermestidae (Coleoptera) from Iraq and Arabian Peninsula. *Fragmenta Faunistica*. 2002, 45 (1): 27-30. <http://dx.doi.org/10.3161/00159301FF2002.45.1.027>
- [52] Veer V, Negi B K, Rao K M. Dermestid beetles and some other insect pests associated with stored silkworm cocoons in India, including a world list of dermestid species found attacking this commodity. *Journal of Stored Products Research*. 1996; 32: 69-89.
- [53] Háva J. *Dermestidae World (Coleoptera)*. 2011; Version February 2018, update January 2021. Available from: www.dermestidae.wz.cz (Accessed on 10 April 2022).
- [54] Thompson J. First record of *Trogoderma variabile* Ballion (Coleoptera, Dermestidae) in Britain. *Entomologist's Monthly Magazine*. 1977; 113: 1-29.
- [55] Hedges S A, Lacey M S. *PCT Field guide for the management of structure infesting beetles, Vol. II Stored Product Beetles/Occasional and Overwintering Beetles*. Franzak and Foster, Cleveland, OH. 1996; 212 pp.
- [56] Tutuncu S, Emekci M. Comparative efficacy of modified atmospheres enriched with carbon dioxide against *Cadra* (= *Ephestia*) *cautella*. *Journal of the Science of Food and Agriculture*. 2019, 99 (13): 5962-5968. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1002/jsfa.9871>
- [57] Xu J, Wang Q, He X Z. Emergence and reproductive rhythms of *Ephestia kuehniella* (Lepidoptera: Pyralidae). *New Zealand Plant Protection*, 2008; 61: 277-282.